

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Illegal Construction in the Italian Regions During the Period 2004-2022

It grew by an average of 12.94% between 2004 and 2022

Istat calculates the value of illegal construction. Illegal construction is defined as the number of illegal constructions per 100 constructions authorized by the Municipalities. The data refers to the period between 2004 and 2022 in the Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of illegal construction in 2022. Basilicata and Calabria are in first place by value of illegal construction in 2022 with a value of 54.1, followed by Campania with a value of 50.4 units and from Sicily with 48.2 units. In the middle of the table are Lazio with a value of illegal construction equal to 20, followed by Umbria and Marche with a value of 10.9 units and Tuscany with 6.8 units. Emilia Romagna closes the ranking with a value of 4.2 units, followed by Trentino Alto Adige and Friuli Venezia Giulia with 3.3 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in illegal construction between 2004 and 2022. Lazio is in first place in terms of value of the percentage change in illegal construction between 2004 and 2022 with a corresponding variation of +73.91%. to a variation from 11.5 units up to 20.00 units. Basilicata and Calabria follow with a variation of +49.45% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 36.2 units up to 54.1 units. Puglia follows with a variation equal to +34.36% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 25.9 units up to 34.8 units. In the middle of the table is Friuli Venezia Giulia with a variation equal to a value of +22.22% corresponding to a growth from 2.7 to 3.3. Sicily follows with a growth of +16.99% corresponding to a change from 41.2 to 48.2 units. Lombardy follows with a value equal to +4.44% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.5 units up to 4.7 units. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a variation of -26.32% corresponding to a decrease from 5.7 units to 4.2 units. Tuscany follows with a variation of -31.31% corresponding to a reduction from 9.9 units to 6.8 units. Liguria closes the ranking with a value of -61.68% corresponding to a variation from 16.7 units up to 6.4 units. On average, illegal construction is expected to grow by 12.94% between 2004 and 2022 corresponding to a variation from 18.1 units up to 20.4 units.

Illegal construction in the Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2022. Illegal construction grew in the following macro-regions: Center with +45.54%, Islands with +21.00%, Southern Italy with +15, 19%, South with 12.57%. There are also macro-regions in which illegal construction has decreased, namely: North with -8.00% and North-West with -14.55%. We can therefore note that the value of illegal construction has significantly increased in the southern macro-regions while it has decreased in the northern macro-regions.

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Three clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Molise, Abruzzo, Puglia, Sardinia;
- Cluster 2: Lombardy, Valle d'Aosta, Piedmont, Emilia-Romagna, Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Trentino Alto Adige, Tuscany, Marche, Umbria, Liguria, Lazio;
- Cluster 3: Calabria, Basilicata, Campania, Sicily.

The following cluster ordering is identified from the point of view of the average, i.e.: $C3 > C1 > C2$. It follows that in first place is cluster 3 made up of four southern regions. This is followed by Cluster 1 made up of the other four southern regions. The central-southern regions, however, are all within cluster 2 characterized by much lower levels of illegal construction compared to the southern regions. We therefore note that the value of illegal construction appears to be very widespread in the southern regions, while this value tends to decrease significantly in the northern regions.

Conclusions. Unauthorized construction grew on average in the Italian regions by 12.94% between 2004 and 2022. We can see the existence of a real gap between the southern regions and the central-northern regions. For example, if we consider illegal construction in Southern Italy in 2022, the value is equal to 42.1 units, while in the North-East the same value is equal to 4.6 and in the North-West it is equal to 4.7 units. It follows that the value of illegal construction in the southern regions is almost 10 times greater than in the northern regions and approximately 2.8 times greater than in the regions of Central Italy. The data highlights an inability of southern municipalities to manage building permits. Furthermore, the high presence of illegal construction could also be an indicator of corruption phenomena and dangerous relationships between companies in the construction sector and municipal administrations. It is very likely that small municipalities are even more affected by illegal building phenomena as highlighted by the data from Basilicata and Calabria. In the northern regions the value of illegal construction is very low. For example, in Trentino Alto Adige and Friuli-Venezia Giulia there are 3.3 illegal building practices for every 100 buildings. The same level for Basilicata and Calabria is 54.1. That is, in Basilicata and Calabria more than half of the buildings are built through illegal construction. The issue of illegal construction becomes serious especially when faced with hydro-geological risks. In fact, the territory of many regions, including southern ones, presents fragilities. Illegal construction therefore constitutes a cost both in terms of illegality and in terms of environmental risks. A possible solution to resolve the issue could consist in the attribution to the regions of procedures in municipalities characterized by high levels of illegal activity, i.e. above 50.00%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

